

**THE DEPARTMENT OF ENERGY'S
SAFEGUARDS AND SECURITY
TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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INTRODUCTION. The Department of Energy (DOE) has had a program that develops technologies to protect sensitive nuclear weapons facilities for more than thirty years. The program is no where near as large as it used to be, but nevertheless exists to help operational security systems overcome technical deficiencies. The mission of the program is overwhelmingly diverse, as it must be to protect an array of assets such as nuclear weapons, special nuclear material in various forms, components of nuclear weapons, and classified nuclear weapons design information. Considering that the nuclear weapons complex consists of dozens of facilities that are scattered all over the United States, and that no two facilities are alike, the technology development mission is very challenging. Complicating matters further is the ever uncertain future of the DOE and the national security role that it will play. Here are some examples of dramatic Departmental mission changes that directly impact our security technology development program:

- Many DOE facility missions have been consolidated, scaled back, or discontinued consistent with a reduced need to process

nuclear materials, resulting in a heightened threat from disgruntled employees;

- Our sprawling nuclear weapons production complex is undergoing major environmental cleanup, and many facilities are being decommissioned and decontaminated (D&D), requiring the use of uncleared workers within sensitive processing facilities, and large quantities of special nuclear material to be placed in storage. New functions such as these are accompanied by new and unique security requirements;
- Remaining facilities and functions will be smaller and will be required to operate more efficiently under tighter budgets, making it difficult to continue the same level of security operations and system maintenance as in the past;
- Large numbers of returning weapons are being accepted by DOE from the Department of Defense for dismantlement, and large quantities of nuclear material are being transferred to DOE from the Former Soviet Union (FSU), placing significant demands on existing material storage and safeguards systems;
- Arms control agreements such as the Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty, Open Skies, and the Chemical Weapons Convention may subject sensitive DOE facilities to unique inspections on short notice; and lastly,
- Federal budget reductions have become common and do not seem to be well directed

considering the relative importance of key-asset protection programs, versus other uses of federal funds.

PROGRAM STRATEGIES. Nine national laboratories participate in this program that now has an annual budget of approximately \$22 million. The technical areas of expertise at these national laboratories are physical security, nuclear material control and accounting, and information security. The strategic goals on which these laboratories focus, in order to address the diverse requirements just described, are as follows:

- Retention of technical expertise in the fundamental safeguards and security disciplines to support a constant flow of new technological protection issues that surface throughout the Department. This is accomplished in part by tasking the national laboratories with technology development projects that address the highest priority needs of our customers;
- Technologies are being developed to support D&D activities. Examples are modular vaults; portable security systems; and nuclear material measurement instruments to account for material that was previously unmeasurable or material that is located in difficult-to-measure locations such as material that has built up over time as a coating on the inside of ducts and pipes;
- Considerable emphasis has been placed on technologies that support the long term storage and disposition of material that has been recovered from weapons, D&D

activities or the FSU. Vault and material surveillance technologies that monitor the location and intrinsic properties of materials in storage (e.g., heat, weight, radiation, etc.) are examples of technologies that support this strategy;

- Emphasis has been shifted from developing very detailed design specifications for procurement purposes, to functional specifications that instead describe what is needed. More importantly, we have been pursuing new alternatives for determining the performance of commercial security equipment, even though we have been very happy having national laboratories such as Sandia provide independent and scientifically sound performance testing. This is because our program resources simply cannot accommodate the explosion of new security products. If you've been to a recent American Society of Industrial Security convention and have seen the thousands of exhibits, you will be able to appreciate the enormous cost that would be required to test all of the new products. We are therefore trying to commercialize as much of these testing capabilities as possible, and have encouraged Sandia, Underwriters Laboratories, national standards organizations, and other federal agencies to develop a common approach for a national security product certification program. The main idea here is that the cost of performance testing must be shifted from the technology development community to the manufacturer/user community, as is the case for product safety testing;

- Although we have been developing technologies that counter the insider threat over the past few years, we have recently begun investigating a more comprehensive insider protection approach that is as transparent to normal plant or office operations as possible, and makes as much use of existing security and other sensors (such as fire alarms) to make the job of the malevolent insider extremely difficult;
- Significant emphasis is still placed on nuclear material control technologies, such as portal detectors, that help alert our sites of an attempt to steal or tamper with special nuclear materials; and,
- Lastly, and one of the areas expected to expand dramatically over the next decade, is that of information security. As you may be aware, an organization can be “brought to its knees” as a result of a virus or a hacker equipped with network penetration skills, such as those virus or hacker tools that can be downloaded from the Internet. Even the control and protection of unclassified technical information, which can be vital to national economic competitiveness, presents a dilemma that will not be solved in the immediate future. Our technology development program will therefore place increasing emphasis on the areas of computer security and information security, in general, in the years to come.

EXAMPLES OF KEY TECHNOLOGY

DEVELOPMENT EFFORTS. A few development efforts will now be highlighted as examples of efforts

currently being sponsored. They are: automated sensor testing devices to help reduce the requirement for personnel to enter vaults containing highly radioactive nuclear materials; a vehicle inspection portal to screen vehicles for hidden passengers, nuclear material, explosives, and other contraband; non-lead and short-range ammunition as an environmentally safe alternative to lead ammunition; a complex-wide visitor access control system to allow all DOE employees to travel to all sites with a commonly recognized credential; automated nuclear material monitoring technologies to provide assurance that material in storage has not been tampered with; laser radar as a potential solution to early warning deficiencies throughout the Department; performance testing standards for many security products to include an automated and consistent standard for assessing the quality of video; low temperature pyrotechnic smoke as a possible adversary delay mechanism; modular vaults to provide temporary protection for nuclear material during D&D activities, and a protection approach for restricted passage areas such as the volume above a tiled ceiling or within a crawl space.

EXTRAMURAL ACTIVITIES. A substantial amount of effort is spent coordinating the developmental efforts of our program with other agencies, such as the Department of Defense and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), not only to prevent possible duplication of efforts, but to take advantage of technologies that others develop. As an example, development of explosive detection equipment has been eliminated from our program because of the substantial investment that is being made by the FAA in this area. Similarly, advances in physical security that have been made within our program for the past 25 years have been shared with the FAA to help them protect their essential facilities

and the flying public.

We are also participating in the General Services Administration's Interagency Advisory Committee on Security Equipment (IACSE), which has been attempting to solve several security equipment procurement and performance characterization issues at the national level, and we currently co-chair the IACSE Intrusion Detection Subcommittee.

Domestic terrorism has recently been receiving increased attention within the United States. Over the past four years, our program has actively supported the efforts of the National Security Council's Technical Support Working Group (TSWG) that sponsors the development of technologies to address the many threats posed by terrorists. We currently chair the Physical Security and Infrastructure Protection Subgroup of the TSWG. The efforts of the TSWG also have impacts beyond "domestic" terrorism because of international bilateral and trilateral efforts that have been established with allied nations in an attempt to share and jointly develop technological innovations to counter or protect against terrorist activities.

SUMMARY. In summary, technology has always played an important role in our cost-effective approach to protecting DOE assets of significant national security interest, and will continue to do so into the foreseeable future. The scope of the program has evolved dramatically since its origin and will continue to do so as the DOE downsizes consistent with its new mission.